

A STUDY ON THE CHANGE BETWEEN TENSILE LOADING AND NATURAL FREQUENCY OF CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Abstract

The characteristic of carbon-carbon materials has attracted engineer's attention in many fields such as aerospace, automotive field, etc. Carbon-carbon composite materials have been used broadly as aircraft, automotive brake disk and a lot more, because of its specific stiffness, specific strength, good fatigue resistance and excellent heat-resisting property in high temperature. This study is focused on the vibration modes of carbon-carbon composite materials. The change of natural frequency is known that it is close to the damage condition under various tensile loadings. Carbon-carbon composite materials are strongly observed with the change of tensile loading and its natural frequency by using accelerometer. The strength and safety factor of carbon-carbon composite materials was acknowledged.

Key words: carbon-carbon composite material, accelerometer

1. Introduction

Carbon/carbon composites (C/Cs) maintain excellent strength and toughness at temperatures exceeding 2273K in a non-oxidizing atmosphere [1]. Because of its low density, high melting point, low thermal expansion, high specific stiffness and mechanical strength at a high temperature and so on, the C/Cs has been widely used in structures of space vehicles, nuclear reactors, aircraft brake, and racing car brake and much more including biocompatible structural elements [2-3]. High fracture toughness is an important advantage of C/Cs [4]. However, a general understanding of C/Cs is still in the primitive stage. For example, even the mechanisms governing the behavior of tensile fractures in C/Cs have not been clarified [1]. As a result, the applications of C/Cs have been restricted to structures in which high strength is not required, but rather in which only high temperature capabilities are necessary. Recently, the present authors and their colleagues have expended a significant amount of effort toward the clarification

of the mechanical behavior of C/Cs especially from the viewpoint of fracture mechanism [5]. However, to the author's knowledge, the tensile strength of C/Cs has not been successfully determined, probably due to problems associated with specimen stacking sequence, specimen preparation, specimen conditioning, environment of testing, specimen alignment and gripping, speed of testing, and the calculation procedures necessary for tensile strength determination [6].

In the present study, an accelerometer is applied for evaluating the vibration modes of carbon-carbon composite under various tensile loadings by using a tensile testing machine. Its natural frequency is accurately measured after applying various tensile loadings on material to observe the strength of the carbon-carbon composite material.

A STUDY ON THE CHANGE BETWEEN TENSILE LOADING AND NATURAL FREQUENCY OF CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITE MATERIALS

2. Testing method

Tensile testing was conducted by using a MTS tensile testing machine (see fig.1). For tensile testing purpose, the model testing ASTM D 3039/D 3039M having the dimension 250 x 25 x 2.5mm was used. In an experiment, five specimens were tested to find its natural frequency after each specimen was loaded by different applied load and the loading speed was 2mm/min. To avoid location fracture at loading points, emery clothes were bonded to the specimens. The specimen was hanged to form a free-free boundary condition. The Accelerometer was mounted onto the specimen using wax so that the accelerometer would have the same vibration. Fig.2 shows an experimental setup for impact hammer test and the real specimen with sketch. The Frequency Response Function (FRF) was measured in the range of 0-5000 Hz to identify the modal characteristics.

Fig.1 Tensile testing machine

Fig.2 Impact hammer testing and real specimen with sketch

(a) Impact hammer s Testing

(b). Real specimen

(c) Sketch of specimen (mm)

3. Results

Basically three specimens were experimented to measure the tensile strength of the carbon-carbon composite material. Fig.3 shows the failure of the material under applied tensile load during testing and three of these specimens were carried out under the same fixed condition, method and applied load to get an accurate result.

Fig.3 Failure of the specimens

Table 1 shows the maximum tensile strength of the three experimented specimens.

Specimen	Maximum tensile strength	Displacement
1	5.37KN	2.399mm
2	5.96KN	2.910mm
3	5.28KN	2.439mm

Fig4. Shows the graph obtained from tensile testing of specimens.

A STUDY ON THE CHANGE BETWEEN TENSILE LOADING AND NATURAL FREQUENCY OF CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Fig.5 shows the result of natural frequency measurement. During tensile testing on tensile testing machine process the specimens were taken out from the testing machine to measure the frequency response functions (FRF) at interval 0-5000 Hz by hanging the specimens to form free-free boundary condition and the accelerometer was mounted onto the specimens. Then FFT was analyzed by hitting the specimens three times using impact hammer in order to get accurate results.

Fig5. The results of natural frequency

4. Discussion

For specimens under tensile loading, its maximum tensile strength was experimentally found to be about 5.5KN as shown in Table1. Thus three specimens were experimented by giving applied load 1KN, 4KN and 5KN to observe the vibration mode and the natural frequency. Table2. Shows the results obtained from the experiment.

Table2. Mode shapes (Hz) and applied load

Tensile Load	1KN	4KN	5KN
Vibration Mode			
1	165	175	187
2	460	465	487
3	784	815	873
4	1114	1120	1137
5	1370	1448	1440
6	1695	1748	1812

Fig6. Shows the results between tensile load and vibration mode obtained from experiment using impact hammer and accelerometer.

A STUDY ON THE CHANGE BETWEEN TENSILE LOADING AND NATURAL FREQUENCY OF CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITE MATERIALS

(a) Tensile loading Vs Frequency

(b) Mode Vs Frequency

Fig6. Applied load and Vibration mode

The graph showed that the frequency increased when tensile loading was added. The reason is the stiffness and the stress of the material changed when tensile loading was applied on specimen. If considered the real C/Cs brake discs, its natural frequency changed due to the high temperature on the friction surface of the discs reached during braking and attributed to the residual tensile stress when the brake discs is cooling down.

5. Conclusion

The following conclusions are made from the tensile testing for C/Cs composite materials.

(1) The maximum tensile strength was accurately

obtained from the experiment which was found cracked in the middle of the specimens during testing. (2) The result of natural frequency measurement showed that the shift configuration which meant that when the tensile loading was added, the natural frequency also increased.

Notes:

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6. References

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